

**INVESTMENTS ATTRACTION REACH MECHANISMS IN
PARTICULAR ABROAD EXPERIENCES**

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Investments attraction to do and of management abroad experience and him in our country application reach possibilities with depends processes study done Investments attraction to do according to of the world leader from countries one was of the United States investment policy , investments attraction to do and them management , arrangement put and control to the road to put ways about and Japan , China , Germany , France , Canada , Great Britain , India , Brazil such as of the world the most big economy have to be countries abroad experience analysis done Developed countries investment attractiveness in our country application reach according to scientific Suggestions and practical recommendations formed.

In our country economic reforms step by step done increase and this in progress the chief reformer of the state the fact that of our country market economy bite to himself typical from the features one is considered b . This is the process investment activities in order put I know about it decisions acceptance requires doing . " Uzbekistan with work desire stated foreign investors with strong contact install the project from the beginning until the end to them help give , simple by doing so to speak , them from the hand leading the result provide need , " he said Shaukat Mirziyoyev [1]. Economy networks investment without putting the activity on the right path , internally and foreign investments attraction to do and efficient mastery their work done without increasing standing up the economy stable to grow , the main capital to update and whole investment-financial in the field structural to changes cannot be reached therefore for state by this reforms in order put stands up The country development and economic situation in improvement foreign of investments place important is considered.

Our country to independence from achieving after many years during investment activity according to experiences collect went To our economy investments attraction of doing active policy take went them of management tactics and strategies by changing saw We are this in our article investments attraction to do and of management abroad experience seeing we go out 76 That is to him according to of the world leader from countries one was of the United

States investment policy , investments attraction to do and them management , arrangement put and control to the road to put ways about stopping let's go USA - economy very developed and legislation system strong country is considered of the United States investment climate enough level bright and is attractive . Current in the day this country foreign investments attraction to do volume according to in the world leader from places one take over is standing That is the world scale about 20 % organize is enough Such great to the results in reaching USA government the economy in development important factor as foreign investments of the country separately to the states necessary powers separate gave That is to him according to in the country territorial management to the authorities investments flow in raising encouragement for common of the country management to the body relatively less did not happen powers is given American government that's it good understand that is , of foreign capital USA economy the introduction only industry , trade and inflationary to the process not but whole of the country national enough for safety effect shows . As a result :→ states and local management to the authorities own of the territory economic development for independence present done is private business and service and of goods export support need→ foreign business capital attraction to do and suitable respectively foreign fifty control the investor as well to →do private of the farm growth encouragement ;→ fiscal in politics motivational shares take to go it is necessary The last one the result that's it shows that i.e this factors now country in the states mutual competition cause out in the country investments about of the law development to himself typical impulse task done gave Meanwhile USA in the economy investments attraction to do and them in management the following series important to himself typical features separate our transition can :→ territorial and of the country take went policy as a result to the economy of investments high flow being provided ;→ capital export and import encourage equal to degree of this as a result country to the status of net importer have was→ of foreign investments high level control to do abuse do (corruption , legislation standards and financial and credit 77 violations of agreements) to road not to be placed ;→ another participants for of the market openness ;→ investment legislation and tax check your system development ;→ investment activity two level in order put system existence That's it to emphasize should be in the USA investments in management economic freedom principles is based on and random to the process serious does not interfere because this road put can't be the border cause releases Such the goal while in the USA external economic activity of institutions main work is a country and his

in the regions maximum export potential expansion , international economic in action possible as long as more participants attraction to do for government by affairs take is going USA economy in 2030 the most big being preserved remains , but his the world gross internal in the product share decreased from 23% in 2021 to 20% . This macroeconomic data gross internal product volume until 2030 the world 20 best in economy big , USA village farm Ministry by counting out organize done (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Countries that will have the world's largest economy in 2030 (trln. dollars)[9]

According to the forecasts, the US will retain its leadership and the country's gross domestic product will reach 24.8 trillion by 2030. is a dollar. The second place is occupied by China, whose gross domestic product is 22.2 trillion. consists of dollars. India is the top three with 6.6 trillion. dollar enters with the gross domestic product. The International Monetary Fund notes that in the last 10 years, India will become the strongest country in the world in terms of production power.

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